

Independent Living Programs: Voice of Youth in Services

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Abstract

Independent Living programs (ILPs) were created to serve transitional aged foster youth by providing them with a smoother transition into adulthood. In order to aid youth with their transitions, ILPs should ensure that key life domains, as noted by Nathan and Chaffers (2022), are incorporated and that youths' voices are being heard throughout their time in the program. Previous research, however, has found that many youth did not feel that their ILPs were beneficial as they still felt unprepared for adulthood and stated not feeling heard during their experiences. A reason why many youth possibly feel unprepared and unheard upon completing the ILP could be due to the programs lack of services in key domains and leaving youth without a voice by not giving them the opportunity to design their plans. A survey was created specifically for independent living coordinators (ILCs), administrators, or directors to understand the approaches used and services they provided youth within their programs. Of the eighty-eight participants that were contacted, eighteen completed the survey. Overall, the findings suggested that ILPs are incorporating all domains and give youth a voice by allowing them to design their plans during their time in the program. However, some domains seem to be targeted more than others and how youth help design their programs differs between ILPs which could be why youth report feeling unprepared upon completing the program and unheard throughout their experiences.

Keywords: Independent living programs (ILPs), Independent living coordinators (ILC), Transitional aged foster youth, Casey Life Assessment, Transitional Independent Living Plan (TILP)

Independent Living Programs: Voice of Youth in Services

In the United States there are nearly 440,000 youth in the child welfare system, and every year approximately 18,000 of these youth age out of the system (Agnihorti et al., 2022).

According to Doucet et al. (2022), aging out is when youth reach a certain age and can no longer receive assistance from the government with services such as financial help or health insurance.

In the United States, the average age for youth to age out is twenty-one years, but varies between states (Doucet et al., 2022). ILPs were developed to assist youth in preparing for the transition out of care but they may not fully address the needs of youth. The current study will address which key domain ILPs provide as well as if and how they include the voice of youth in these plans. First, however, it is important to understand what past research has found and understand how and why it is important for this study.

Research by Arnett (2015) has shown that young adults rely on their families for emotional and financial well-being, and youth who have that support are better able to transition into adulthood rather than those who do not have it. This process is known as emerging adulthood, where young adults do not fully reach adulthood until about twenty-nine years old. (Arnett, 2015). According to Doucet et al. (2022), when youth experience emerging adulthood they have a greater opportunity to build relationships with others around them who will help guide and support them throughout their transition and stay with them throughout adulthood. However, foster youth who do not have stable adult relationships or support, face the opposite of emerging adulthood, what is known as instant adulthood. This is where young adults are

expected to take on the responsibilities of adulthood as soon as they exit foster care even though they do not have the adequate resources to do so and have no one to help them (Doucet et al., 2022). For example, the Children's Bureau (2023), website indicates that by the age of nineteen only about 50% of youth have a high school diploma or an equivalent and only 23% were employed. Due to a lack of income most foster youth face challenges in the housing and life skills domain as well. Shpiegel and Cascardi (2015) found that 16% of former foster youth were experiencing or had experienced homelessness at one point during their adulthood journey. As a result of lacking resources within these certain domains most youth also faced challenges in the mental health domain. This is shown in a study by Havlicek et al. (2013), where the authors found that foster youth are twice as likely to experience PTSD and five times more likely to experience some form of anxiety compared to youth who had never been in foster care. Former foster youth not only face adversity in these areas, but also in the support domain as most have very limited or no social and emotional support. Out of the 18,000 youth that are estimated to age out every year only sixty-nine percent, about 12,000, reported having at least one person in their life who they feel supported by (Nathans & Chaffers, 2022).

According to Rutman and Hubberstey (2016), youth who have never been in foster care usually have people around them their whole life to help them transition into adulthood. Foster youth, however, do not have the same level of support as their non-foster youth peers and do not learn the skills needed to transition to adulthood and, as a result, many are not adequately prepared to meet the challenges of adulthood (Rutman & Hubberstey, 2016). For example, obtaining secure housing, education and basic life skills tend to go unmet for many youth throughout adulthood due to a lack of resources, such as money or transportation. However, when youth have support from other adults around them they gain access to new resources and are offered support in different

domains as identified by Nathans and Chaffers (2022). In order to give youth the support needed ILPs have independent living coordinators (ILCs) who, according to Nathans and Chaffers (2022) work with youth to help them reach their individual needs. By ILCs providing support for transitional aged foster youth in the ILPs, youth have better outcomes when transitioning into adulthood by using key domains and giving youth a voice (Nathans & Chaffers, 2022).

The support from ILCs is important to help minimize the various challenges that transitional aged foster youth face. For example, 35% of emancipated foster youth claim to have needs which are never taken care of ranging from needs such as new clothing or transportation to mental health and social needs (Katz, 2015). These challenges are caused from various needs that go unmet by foster youth. The needs that foster youth should be receiving help in have been identified by Nathans and Chaffers (2022), and make up of seven domains, which include education, employment, housing, life skills, physical and mental health, support, and prevention. ILPs were created as a way to help transitional aged foster youth meet their needs in these key domains. In 1999 ILPs were created and approved through the John H. Chafee Foster Care Independence Act (FCIA), which were designed to support emancipated foster youth by providing them with a smoother transition into adulthood while simultaneously reducing instant adulthood percentages (Kim et al., 2019). The seven key domains which Independent Living Programs assist youth with can be grouped into two broad areas, tangible domains that include education, employment, housing, and life skills; and intangible domains that include physical and mental health, support, and prevention.

Research has found that all domains should be targeted when helping youth transition into adulthood (Nathans & Chaffers, 2020). However, what is still being researched is how to create a system that will target youths' individual needs (Kothari, 2020). In order to be able to meet the

individual needs of each youth, ILPs assign an independent living coordinator (ILCs) to each youth, which addresses another important domain, known as support. Research has shown if foster youth had any sort of stable relationships with an adult figure, whether that be a social worker, a permanent guardian, teacher, or anyone from their community that could help them throughout the process, it would significantly increase youths' opportunity to successfully transition into adulthood (Rutman & Hubberstey, 2016). With support from professionals and other adults in their life, foster youth report having someone to rely on and feel comfortable when building relationships with them. These newly relationships formed are crucial for the transition into adulthood as they play a significant role in targeting Nathan and Chaffers' (2022) intangible support domain and give youth access to resources in all the other domains.

Relationships with their ILCs help youth set goals which will be beneficial for youth in their transition through adulthood. ILCs assess youth upon entering the program and create a plan based on youth's needs (Nathans & Chaffers, 2022). Although ILCs assess youth on their needs to create a plan, ILPs have still tend to focus greater attention on tangible domains by helping youth acquire daily life skills such as finding employment, cooking, budgeting, and education. These skills are important as foster youth lack skills within these areas; however, many ILPs tend to forget about the intangible domains. Intangible domains are a crucial part of youths' development that allows them to have a smoother transition into adulthood. Not targeting these intangible domains negatively impacts youth, as they do not get help with their mental health needs and have a harder time meeting their emotional and social needs as well. This can set them back on meeting their tangible goals and success (Doucet et al., 2022).

Due to the lack of help with their mental health and not having social support, many foster youth have reported feeling alone and unheard throughout their time in ILPs. Many youth also feel

that their experiences were not beneficial toward their transition into adulthood (Doucet et al., 2022). The reason many youths feel this way can be due to ILCs not incorporating youths' voices into the program enough, or how they approach youths' feedback and opinions. As stated by Nathans and Chaffers (2022), in order for ILP's to be more effective ILC's should not only support youth in their needs but allow them to participate when designing their individual plans. Youth should also be able to review their plans and revise as necessary every few months in order to ensure their goals are on track to be met. ILC's should also verify that youths' plans include every key domain, as indicated by Nathans and Chaffers (2022), to ensure ILPs are providing a smoother transition into adulthood. Since ILPs are providing youth with someone who will support them through their transition to adulthood, youth should leave these programs feeling supported and independent. However, as we know from previous research most youth who participate in ILPs do not feel that way (Doucet et al., 2022). Therefore, this study draws upon the domains identified by Nathans and Chaffers (2022) in order to understand which domains are being used in ILPs and also identifies if and how youths' voices are being used within ILPs.

Method

Participants

ILP coordinators, directors, and administrators found on a 2022 California Independent Living Program Narrative Report were contacted through email. A total of 88 participants received an email and 39 participants responded, but only 18 completed the survey.

Survey Design

To conduct the study a survey was created using both qualitative and quantitative measures. The quantitative measures asked about the ILC's training approaches used to help

youth, background information on the program, services their ILPs are using, and the level of youth involvement. The qualitative measures the number of session and length of sessions that youth received with their ILCs, the number of trainings required for ILCs, and the number of services provided for youth.

Measures

ILP Domains

This study measured the use of key domains, noted by Nathans and Chaffers (2022), in ILPs by having participants select all of the domains that their program uses. To understand which domains ILPs are using participants were asked “What area(s) does the program target? Check all that apply.” The options included: general living skills, employment, education, social support and relationships, mental health, financial independence, housing and other.

Youth Input

How youths’ voices were incorporated in the programs was also measured. To measure this, participants were first asked “Does your program provide an opportunity for youth to help plan their ILP services?” If the participants indicated “yes”, then participants were asked “Can you share how your program provides youth the opportunity to help plan their ILP service(s)?”

Procedure

After approval by the CSUF Institutional Review Board, an email was sent to eighty-eight independent living coordinators, directors, and or administrators in the state of California. The participants were selected from a 2022 California Independent Living Program Narrative Report.

The survey was created through Qualtrics and consisted of twenty open-ended questions, and fifteen multiple choice questions. To avoid multiple responses from each ILP, participants asked were asked in the email that only one independent living coordinator, administrator, or director from each program complete the survey. Before beginning the study participants were asked to consent to the study and were informed that they can complete it on their own time. Participants were also asked to indicate the name of their agency, but all answers were kept anonymous. The survey took approximately ten minutes to complete. Of the eighty-eight agencies contacted, thirty-nine (44%) participated and eighteen (20%) participants completed the survey.

Plan of Analysis

After all data was collected on Qualtrics the data was transferred into an SPSS data file. Descriptive statistics examined which key domains were provided by the ILP and if the ILPs provided youth with a voice. A table was also created to show how opportunities were given to youth to use their voice by separating participants open-ended responses to individual approaches and group approaches.

Results

In the survey participants were asked to select all the services provided in their program. These services were taken from the domains indicated by Nathans and Chaffers (2022). As shown on Figure 1, services for all key domains were provided to youth. Results showed that 100% of respondents indicated their ILP provide services in the housing, social support (and relationships), education, employment, and general living skills domains. For the financial independence domain, 94% indicated that they provide services in that area. As for the mental

health domain only 83% provide services in that area. A total of 38% of respondents also indicated that they provide other types of services. Some of the other types of services included transportation, sexual health and vocational trainings.

The survey also focused on youths' voices in the programs. Participants were asked to indicate if their ILP incorporated youths' voices by giving them an opportunity to help design their individual plans for their time throughout the program. As shown in Figure 2, the results showed that 92% (13) of participants provide youth an opportunity to plan their services. If participants selected yes, they were asked to explain how their program provides youth with opportunities to help. The answers from participants varied: some programs allowed youth to address needs through individual input alone, while others addressed the youths' needs through group input (see Table 1).

Discussion

The aims of this study were: 1) to understand whether ILPs were incorporating domains as noted by Nathans and Chaffers (2022) and 2) understand if ILPs were giving youth a voice in creating their individual plans during their time in the ILP. Addressing the first aim, results indicated that all domains, except for the domain of mental health were incorporated by all programs (see Figure 1). The second aim was to understand if ILPs give youth a voice in creating their individual plans throughout their time in the ILP. Results indicated that most ILPs do provide youth a voice in creating their own plans in the ILP, but how they do so differed between programs.

Addressing the importance of key domains in the ILPs were highlighted by Agnihotri (2022), who identified eight different areas transitional aged youth need while transitioning into

adulthood. These areas include health, basic needs, conduct and victimization, employment, education, social support (and relationships), resilience (and psychological empowerment) and general living skills. Nathans and Chaffers (2022) referenced these domains and reclassified them into seven different domains that are broken down further into tangible and intangible domains. Nathans and Chaffers (2022) grouped the tangible domains by classifying them into domains that have statistics which are easier to measure. For example, it is easier to see how many youth have housing or have received an education. On the other hand, Nathans and Chaffers (2022) grouped the intangible domains by classifying them into domains which are harder to measure. For example, some statistics may report that a certain percentage of foster youth face challenges with a mental health illness, however, that is only accounting for the percentage that have been diagnosed and have access to mental health services.

Education was one of the identified key domains that ILPs targeted. This domain is important because foster youth usually encounter more challenges throughout their educational journeys. For example, being unprepared for school due to various changes throughout their lives such as placement instability and constantly changing schools (Unrau et al., 2017). The authors found that a result of this lack in stability, only 50% of youth in foster care finish high school. Further, less than 20% of those who graduated high school attend college, 3% of whom graduate from college (Unrau et al., 2017). Another important domain was related to employment. This domain is important for ILPs to target as it has been found that transitional aged foster youth are less likely to be employed and many stay unemployed until their mid-twenties (Dworsky & Gitlow, 2017). High rates of unemployment and low graduation rates make foster youth more vulnerable to poverty, as they do not acquire the necessary life skills to have a smooth transition to adulthood (Liu et al., 2019). We also know that it is important that ILPs aid youth in their

housing and other life skill domains such as job preparation, saving money, and using technology. All ILPs surveyed identified that they cover these areas.

Most respondents also indicated that they provide youth support in the intangible domain area of support. Having support is important as it can prevent youth from various risks that transitional aged foster youth face, these include; homelessness and lack of health insurance causing them to have greater undiagnosed mental health illness (Armstrong-Heimsoth et al., 2021, 295). However, Armstrong-Heimsoth's et al. (2021) study found that transitional aged foster youth do not ask for help because they may have a lack of trust due to their past experiences. Yet, it is important that youth ask for help as those who reported having someone who supports them helps build their trust and motivation to access other services that they may not be receiving help in when transiting to adulthood (Armstrong-Heimsoth et al., 2021).

Some of the services that transitional aged foster youth have trouble accessing are mental health services, another important domain referenced by Nathans and Chaffers (2022). Although the ILPs are targeting most of the domains, mental health was the one domain that was not targeted by all ILPs. This could be because youth may have their own therapists outside of the ILP and ILC's do not want to interrupt the work and progress that is being made with youth and their therapists. However, previous research by Armstrong-Heimsoth et al. (2021), has found that some youth mentioned needing assistance with accessing mental health services since most of the time, when they were in care, therapy was only offered as a reward for being obedient (p.295). Nathans and Chaffers (2022) also found that transitional aged foster youth face more mental health challenges than youth who were never in foster care. This can be one of foster youths' biggest obstacle, making it challenging for them to develop skills in other domains. For example, compared to their non-foster youth peers, foster youth were twice as likely to

experience PTSD, three times more likely to have ADHD, and four times more likely to experience a conduct disorder (Nathans & Chaffers, 2022). Foster youth were also more likely to be prescribed with psychotropic medication according to Nathans and Chaffers (2022) as they had five times higher rate of anxiety, six times more likely to display behavioral problems and seven times more likely to be depressed compared to their non-foster youth peers. Due to foster youths' higher risk of facing a mental health challenge, this should be a domain that is covered by all ILPs. Apart from assuring that youth are receiving help with their mental health, it is also important that youth feel heard.

The second aim of this study was to see if youths' voices were being incorporated into the ILP. The results indicated that ILPs do give youth a voice by allowing them to give their opinions and feedback in creating their individual plans. However, the way in which youths' voices were incorporated differed between programs. Some programs used an individual approach for youth to use their voice. This means that ILPs let youth participate in designing their individual plans by allowing them to plan it alone, or with minimal support from others. For example, when asked how they provided youth with an opportunity to use their voice in the ILP one responded indicated, "TILP inclusion, person centered planning with assistance, minimal support or, independently." Transitional independent living plans are plans that are meant to be created for youth in the ILPs to set goals and write down needs. Some ILPs have staff or other foster youth help write plans, while others allow youth to write the TILPs on their own. By letting youth design their own plans alone, or with minimal help, allows youth to feel that their voices are being incorporated more and helps them feel more independent.

As noted on Table 1, other ILPs used a group approach. This means that youth design their individual plans with a group made up of other youth and staff. Some programs make youth

meet with other youth who are currently in, or were in, the ILP and make a plan together that targets all of their needs. Some ILPs also use assessments in order to understand what the needs of all youth in the ILP are and incorporate them into every youth's plan. The assessments used by ILPs include Transitional Independent Living Plans (TILP) and the Casey Life Skills Assessment. TILPs are plans developed by foster youth by having them list their top goals and identify areas where they feel they need more assistance. Creating this TILP should allow for a smoother transition into adulthood as it states all of their goals and areas that need more assistance (Lens-Rashid, 2018). The Casey Life Skill assessment, as discussed by Kinarsky (2017), is an assessment tool created by Cassey Family Programs. Youth's responses to the questions of the assessments gives ILCs a greater understanding of what areas their youth need more help in. Both approaches allow youth to voice their individual needs rather than doing what the ILCs believe is best for them. In a study conducted by Geenen and Powers (2017), some youth who completed ILPs stated feeling pushed by their ILCs to do something they did not need or want, simply because the ILC believed it was good for them. By the ILCs pushing youth to do certain things, many felt that they missed out on opportunities to do what they felt would be beneficial to them (Geenen & Powers, 2007). In a separate study conducted by Doucet et al. (2022), youth reported that ILCs were sometimes too involved with their case which led to them being interdependent rather than independent. Therefore, it is important that youth can assist in designing their individual plans based on their own needs, as shown in these assessments. The plans should also be created by youth individually, with assistance when needed, to help them have a better opportunity of meeting all their goals and needs.

Limitations and Strengths

One of the study's limitations is the small response rate. Of the eighty-eight ILPs that were emailed, only eighteen completed the survey. The information used to select participants was gathered from a narrative report for ILPs in California from 2022. Although the narrative report was only a year old, it had some outdated information on the participants. For example, some emails no longer existed, and others no longer held that position. Since the narrative report only included information for ILPs in California, it does not allow us to know if the findings are generalizable to ILPs nationwide. Another limitation is the number of questions on the survey. Since no incentives were awarded for participating in the study, the survey was kept short to encourage a higher response rate. Since the questions were limited, the survey did not ask participants to describe why they did or did not provide services in each domain. The project still had strengths despite the limitations. One of the strengths was having open-ended questions, which allowed ILPs to provide more information and gives further detail to help understand their approaches. The study gives direction for future research by showing that mental health is a key domain that is not targeted as often as the other key domains. Future research can help ILPs understand how they can incorporate mental health into their programs. This study also lists different ways that ILPs give youth a voice in designing their plans for the program.

Conclusion

In conclusion, most of the ILPs surveyed do include services targeting key domains in and give youth a voice by providing them with the opportunity to help design their individual plans for their time in the ILP. Although ILPs provide services in the domains, many ILPs did not target the mental health domain, which is said to be the greatest challenge for youth because it affects all the other domains. The lack of services in the mental health domain could be why many youth state feeling unprepared for adulthood even after completing their ILP. For the

second measure of the study, all but one ILP incorporated youths' voices but how they did so differed between ILPs. For example, some ILPs made youth design a plan to fit the entire groups needs rather than having them design a plan to fit their own needs. Not allowing youth to express their own needs could be a possible reason why youth state not feeling heard during their time in ILPs. This study provides suggestions for future research, one of them being is to find new ways to help youth with mental health services and how to incorporate them into the ILP.

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Figure 1

Key Domains in ILPs

Figure 2

Youth's Voices in ILPs

Table 1

Opportunities Provided for Youth to use their voice when designing their plans.

Group Approach	Individual Approach
<p>“Our Leadership Committee/Youth Council meet a minimum of once monthly and provide ILP staff with class suggestions, trip planning, outings, etc.”</p>	<p>“They complete the Casey Life Skills Assessment, TILP and Case Plan”</p>
<p>“Staff contact youth individually and poll them as a group to assess what services are needed.”</p>	<p>“They identify their goals that get put into their TILP and services are somewhat crafted to help the youth achieve those goals”</p>
<p>“We have a youth advisory board comprised of current or former foster youth.”</p>	<p>“TILP completion, youth directed goal setting/motivational interviewing, voluntary services”</p>
<p>“Transitional Living Case Planning with ILP staff and social worker”</p>	<p>“TILP inclusion, person centered planning with assistance, minimal support, or independently”</p>
	<p>“We simply ask them what they would like to learn”</p>